

Unveiling the anticancer efficacy of *Rauwolfia serpentina* and *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* herbal nanopowders

Padmaja Vasa ^{* a}, Babu Kakumanu ^b, Rosaiah Gorrepati ^b

a. Department of Botany, Dr. V. S. Krishna Government Degree College (A),

Visakhapatnam – 530022, Andhra Pradesh, India

* Corresponding author : Padmaja Vasa

b. Department of Botany and Microbiology, Acharya Nagarjuna University Nagarjuna nagar,

Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India.

*Corresponding author .

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Abstract

Plants have been utilized for medicinal purposes globally due to their superior therapeutic value and current trends promote the utilization of natural products in healthcare. The implementation of nanotechnology in healthcare has led to the creation of an innovative drug delivery system. The shortcomings of conventional herbal medications are addressed by plant-based nanopowders, which show promising results in pharmacological and biological applications. Two significant therapeutic plants that are members of the Apocyanaceae family are *Rauwolfia serpentina*, often known as Sarpagandha, and *Rauwolfia tetraphylla*. They have long been used in traditional Indian medicine to cure a number of ailments. Numerous phytochemicals, including alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, steroids, tannins and alcohols are abundant in both of these plants. Phytosynthesized nanopowders have promising biomedical and pharmaceutical applications. Thus, for the first time in our current study, we have used a mechanical technique of high energy ball milling to create nanopowder from shade-dried roots and leaves of our experimental plants without the use of hazardous chemicals. Ball mill-produced nanopowders are studied using a variety of techniques, including Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy and UV-VIS spectroscopy. The cytotoxic activity of methanolic nanopowder extracts of *Rauwolfia serpentina* root and *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* leaf was assessed using the MTT test against three distinct cell lines: A549 (Human Lung Cancer Cell line), HCT 116 (Human Colon Cancer Cell line) and HL 60 (Human Acute Leukemia Cell line) and compared to ascertain their potential.

Key Words

Rauwolfia serpentina, *Rauwolfia tetraphylla*, Ball milling, Nanopowders, Cell lines.

I. Introduction

Richard Philips Feynman's seminal 1959 speech, "There is Plenty of Room at the Bottom," threw light on the challenge of controlling and modifying things at a small scale—now known as the nanoscale. The idea of nanotechnology, which has the potential to transform the world, was born out of this talk. Nanotechnology, one of the promising technologies of 21st century, focuses on materials and devices between 1-100 nanometers, where nanoparticles exhibit unique properties due to their small size [[17],[3]]. This field has rapidly advanced with improved synthesis and characterization, leading to wide applications across various fields. Nanoparticles can be synthesized through physical, chemical and biological methods. While physical and chemical methods are fast, they involve toxic chemicals and harmful by-products [14]. The biological, or "Green Synthesis " method using plants is eco-friendly, cost-effective and simple. It utilizes plant phytochemicals to create stable, pharmacologically active nanoparticles, offering a safer and sustainable alternative to traditional methods [27]. Herbal plants have long been used for medicinal purposes due to their therapeutic value and minimal side effects. Advances in nanotechnology have led to the use of plant-derived nanoparticles in novel drug delivery systems (NDDS), improving treatment effectiveness and stability [2].

Ball milling is a simple, cost-effective top-down technique used to produce nanopowders by breaking down coarse particles into finer ones. It preserves the chemical composition of the original material and can be applied to a wide range of materials [33]. Studies on herbal nanoparticle synthesis through this method are limited. In the current study, a new approach was developed for synthesizing herbal nanopowders using ball milling from roots and leaves of test plants. Nanoparticle characterization techniques like UV-VIS spectroscopy, SEM, XRD and FTIR help determine their size, shape and morphology, which impact their properties and applications [7]. Exploring medicinal plant's biological activity can reveal their therapeutic potential and lead to the creation of novel medications and therapies with a range of benefits that include antibacterial, anticancer, antimicrobial, antioxidant properties etc. [29].

Rauwolfia serpentina and *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* are medicinal plants in the Apocyanaceae family, known for their bioactive compounds, particularly alkaloids like Reserpine and Ajmaline. *R. serpentina*, wonder drug of India, is widely used for treating hypertension and snake bites [31], while *R. tetraphylla* serves as a substitute for *Rauwolfia serpentina* in traditional medicine, containing alkaloids, flavonoids and other bioactive compounds [12],[13]. The study aims to synthesize nanopowders from roots of *Rauwolfia serpentina* and leaves of *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* using ball milling and compare their anticancer efficacy, which could enhance the therapeutic potential of these plants.

II. Materials and Methods

Nowadays, research on medicinally significant plants and their bioactive components is crucial. Two highly valuable and medicinally significant plants of Apocyanaceae are *Rauwolfia serpentina* and *Rauwolfia tetraphylla*. Numerous studies have been conducted on these two plants from a medicinal standpoint so far. However, there is currently a lack of comparative medicinal investigation of herbal nanopowders made from the leaves of *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* and roots of *Rauwolfia serpentina*. The following structured approach clearly outlines the kinds of materials and techniques utilized to investigate a comparative assessment of anticancer efficacy of *R. serpentina* and *R. tetraphylla*.

Collection and authentication of plant Samples

Healthy and fresh *Rauwolfia serpentina* plants were collected from the Chintapalli/Paderu area (18° 4' 59.88" N and 82° 40' 1.20" E) in Visakhapatnam District, Andhra Pradesh, India and *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* plants were collected from Srikakulam (18° 17' 49.1064" N and 83° 53' 48.4152" E) in Srikakulam District of Andhra Pradesh, India. These plants were identified, authenticated (ANUBH01192, ANUBH01193) in Herbarium of Department of Botany & Microbiology, Acharya Nagarjuna University, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Synthesis of herbal nanopowders

For the synthesis of nanopowders, the roots of *R. serpentina* and leaves of *R. tetraphylla* were isolated. To get rid of dust particles from the surface, plant parts were cleaned twice with tap water and then again with double-distilled water for many times. After being cleaned, the roots and leaves were allowed to air dry for three weeks in the shade. Shade-dried roots and leaves were ground into coarse powders using a mixture grinder initially. These were subsequently put through a ball milling process by using Ball Mill (PM 200 RETSCH) using 7mm Zirconium balls at the Nanotechnology department of Andhra University, Visakhapatnam. Nanopowders of roots and leaves were produced by milling the powders for 25 hours at 500 rpm. The synthesized nanopowders were then characterized by physical and chemical characterization methods.

Characterization of herbal nanopowders

(A) Physical characterization

X-Ray diffraction (XRD) studies

The face-center cubic crystalline nature of synthetic root and leaf powders from experimental plants is examined using X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) research. Using an XPERT-PRO Diffractometer (PANALYTICAL) set to 45 KV and 40 mA, the dry powder was applied to an XRD copper grid and examined for nanopowders. The spectrum is recorded using CuK alpha radiation of 1.5406 Å in the range of 2θ from 10° to 91°. The crystallite domain size of nanopowders is calculated using the Debye-Scherrer formula, which is calculated from the width of XRD peaks.

$$D = 0.94 \lambda / \beta \cos \theta$$

The formula involves calculating the average crystallite domain size perpendicular to the reflecting planes (D), based on the X-ray wavelength (1.5406 angstroms) (λ), full width at half maximum (FWHM) i.e β and diffraction angle (θ).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The morphology and microstructure of herbal nanopowders was analyzed using Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM). A thin film was created under vacuum by spreading the material on a carbon-coated copper grid for SEM analysis. With a resolution of 1.2 nm at 30 KV and 32 nm at 1 KV, SEM analysis was performed using a Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM) - 7100 F/JEOL India Pvt., Ltd., Bangalore.

(B) Chemical characterization

UV-Visible spectroscopy

For optical investigation, the herbal nanopowders of *Rauwolfia serpentina* roots and *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* leaves were dissolved in carbinol and put in a quartz cuvette at room temperature. All of the herbal nanopowders absorption spectra were acquired using the Shimadzu UV-Visible Spectrophotometer UV-2400 PC series, which operated at a resolution of 1.0 nm and covered wavelength ranges of 200–800 nm.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

The FTIR SHIMADZU Spectrometer (IR Affinity 1S) was used to get the spectra of the root and leaf herbal nanopowders from both test plants. The spectra were obtained using KBr pellet and an average of 10 scans per sample, in the frequency range of 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} , with a resolution of 4 ($1/\text{cm}$). In transmittance mode, these pellets were employed for FTIR investigation. 200:1 KBr, nanopowders were mixed to create the pellet.

Anticancer activity

Rauwolfia serpentina root and *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* leaf methanolic nanopowder extracts were evaluated for cytotoxic activity using MTT assay. The MTT assay is a colorimetric assay that uses the reduction of the yellow water-soluble tetrazolium dye to formazan crystals to measure cell growth and cytotoxicity. When MTT is reduced to insoluble formazan crystals by mitochondrial lactate dehydrogenase, which is produced by living cells, the result is a purple color that can be measured spectrophotometrically at 570 nm and whose intensity is proportional to the number of viable cells. [[1], [21]].

Maintenance of cell lines

The human lung cancer cell line A549, the human colon cancer cell line HCT 116 and the human acute leukemia cell line HL 60 were acquired from National Centre for Cell Sciences (NCCS) in Pune, India. In the CO₂ Incubator, the A549 and HCT116 cells were kept in DMEM High Glucose Media, while the HL 60 cells were kept in RPMI 1640 Media supplemented with 10% FBS and 1% antibiotic-antimycotic, in an atmosphere of 5% CO₂, 18–20% O₂ and 37 °C temperature. The chosen cells were cultivated in culture medium at a density of 20,000 cells per well in a 96-well plate for the MTT assay, and they were then incubated for 12 hours at CO₂ incubator.

Procedure

In a 96-well plate, 200 μl of cell suspension was seeded without the test agent at the necessary cell density of 20,000 cells per well. The cells were given roughly twenty-four hours to grow. Following that, the cells were incubated for 48 hours at 37°C with 5% CO₂ atmosphere containing different sample concentrations in 0.1% DMSO. Plates were removed from the incubator after the incubation period, cleaned with phosphate buffered saline (pH 7.4), and then treated with MTT reagent until the final concentration was 0.5 mg/mL of total volume. During the three-hour incubation period, plates were shielded from light by covering them with aluminum foil. Following the removal of the MTT reagent, 100 μl of DMSO was added to dissolve the MTT formazan crystals. Complete dissolution might require pipetting and gentle stirring, particularly in dense cultures. Cells with

metabolically active mitochondria reduce the MTT salt to chromophore formazan crystals as a precipitate at the end of the incubation period. Using a spectrophotometer or an ELISA reader, the optical density of solubilized crystals in DMSO was determined at reference wavelengths of 570 and 630 nm. $Y = Mx + C$, the linear regression equation, was used to calculate the IC50 value.

The viability graph was used to determine the M and C values for $Y = 50$.

The following formula was used to determine the percentage growth inhibition.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = 100 (\text{Control} - \text{Treatment}) / \text{Control}$$

III. Results and Discussion

In our present work, due to growing demand for the synthesis of nanopowders from medicinal plants and herbs, we have synthesized nanopowders from two medicinal plants of Apocynaceae i.e. *Rauwolfia serpentina* and *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* using physical procedure Ball milling. This top-down ball milling technique was proved as an effective approach in synthesizing herbal nanopowders when compared to other hazardous chemical means. The synthesized nanopowders of these plants were subjected to characterization and evaluation of anticancer activity. Apart from that an attempt was also made for the first time on comparative analysis of cold extracted methanol nanopowders of root of *Rauwolfia serpentina* and leaf of *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* to determine their relative anticancer efficacy on three different cell lines.

Characterization of Herbal Nanopowder

(A) Physical characterization

XRD Analysis

By using XRD analysis, the size of produced nanoparticles may be ascertained. Figure 1 depicts the XRD pattern of the nanopowders produced from root of *Rauwolfia serpentina* and leaf of *Rauwolfia tetraphylla*. Table I shows the crystalline grain size determined using the Scherrer formula.

Figure 1 (A) XRD analysis of *R. serpentina* root

(B) XRD analysis of *R. tetraphylla* leaf

Table I. XRD data of herbal nanoparticles of *R. serpentina* and *R. tetraphylla*

Plant Part	Peak Position (2θ)	Average Crystalline Size (nm)
<i>R. serpentina</i>		
Root	27.064330	26.16 nm
<i>R. tetraphylla</i>		
Leaf	31.714910	10.57nm

The XRD pattern reveals the crystalline nature of nanoparticles in both these plants. According to the Scherrer formula, the average nanoparticle size of *Rauwolfia serpentina* roots and *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* leaves was 26.16 nm and 10.57 nm, respectively. The size of the herbal nanopowders produced in this study was in line with the herbal nanopowders made from *Rhizophora apiculata* (14.38 nm) [30] and smaller than the leaf nanopowders made using metallic methods, such as the CuO nanoparticles of *R. serpentina* (16.25 nm) by Lingaraju et al, 2015 [19], the AgNO₃ nanoparticles of *R. tetraphylla* (15.06 nm) [32] and the root AgNPs of *R. serpentina* (16.25 nm) by Bonigala et al. [5].

SEM Analysis

Nanopowders can be examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to determine their size and structure. The SEM pictures of *Rauwolfia serpentina* root nanopowders and *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* leaf nanopowders are shown in Figure 2. *Rauwolfia serpentina*'s root nanoparticles and *Rauwolfia tetraphylla*'s leaf nanoparticles are spherical. The root nanoparticles in *R. serpentina* ranged in size from 45 to 65 nm and the produced leaf nanoparticles in *R. tetraphylla* ranged in size from 41.5 nm to 44.1 nm.

Figure 2. (A) SEM analysis of *R. serpentina*

(B) SEM analysis of *R. tetraphylla*

The shape of herbal nanopowders deduced through SEM reveals spherical shape. These results tallied with the shape of silver nanoparticles [5] and gold nanoparticles synthesized from *Rauwolfia serpentina* root (20-70 nm) [4]. SEM measurements revealed root nanopowders of *Rauwolfia serpentina* and leaf nanopowders of *R. tetraphylla*, with sizes ranging from 45 to 65 nm.

(B) Chemical characterization

UV-Visible spectral Analysis

UV-Visible spectroscopy is a simple and effective tool for characterizing and detecting nanopowders. The UV-Visible spectral profile at room temperature was chosen to be 200-800 nm in wavelength. UV-Visible spectroscopy was used to study the methanolic root and leaf nanopowders of two medicinal plants from the Apocynaceae family, *Rauwolfia serpentina* and *Rauwolfia tetraphylla*. The root nanopowders of *R. serpentina* exhibited surface plasmon resonance peaks at 360.50 nm, 307.50 nm, 291.50 nm, 224.50 nm and 205.50 nm in their UV-visible spectrum profile (Figure 3A). The UV-Visible spectrum profile of *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowders showed peaks centered near 664 nm, broad peak at 363.50 nm, 289.50 nm, narrow peaks at 224 nm and 206 nm (Figure 3B).

Figure 3. (A) UV-Vis analysis of *R. serpentina*(B) UV-Vis analysis of *R. tetraphylla*

The formation of herbal nanopowders was further confirmed using UV-VIS spectra. The peaks formed by the samples of *R. serpentina* and *R. tetraphylla* within the wavelength range of 200nm to 800nm demonstrate nanopowder production. The UV-Vis spectra of *R. serpentina* root nanopowders revealed broad peaks at 360.50 nm and 307.50 nm, similar to the spectra of *R. tetraphylla* leaf, which shows a broad peak at 363.50 nm, indicating the formation of herbal nanopowders. It also agrees with findings derived from herbal nanoparticles synthesised from *Tridax procumbens* leaf by ball milling [16]. The UV-Visible spectrum shows the presence of flavonoids since usually two absorption maxima in the range of 230-290nm and 300-350nm exist [28].

FTIR Analysis

FT-IR spectroscopy is a potent tool for identifying the functional groups found in plant samples with its 400–4000 cm^{-1} IR region range. The FT-IR analysis clearly shows the presence of several functional groups in nanopowders. The FTIR spectrum of root nanopowders of *Rauwolfia serpentina* and leaf nanopowders of *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* were presented in figure 4 and table II.

Figure 4 (A) FTIR spectrum of *R. serpentina* root samples(B) FTIR spectrum of *R. tetraphylla* leaf samples

Table II. FTIR spectroscopical data of *R. serpentina* and *R. tetraphylla*

Wave Number (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Groups
<i>R. serpentina</i> Root	
2343.59	CO ₂
2243.29	C ≡ N stretch
2926.11(weak peak)	Alkane C-H stretch
3527.92, 3421.83, 3414.12 (strong broad peaks)	Intermolecular Alcohol O-H stretch
3857.76, 3844.26(weak sharp peaks)	N-H stretch
<i>R. tetraphylla</i> Leaf	
3423.76, 3439.19(strong broad peaks)	Intermolecular Alcohol O-H stretch
2924.18(strong sharp peak)	Alkane C-H stretch
1639.55,1629.90 (strong broad peaks)	C=C stretch alkene
1442.80(weak, broad peak)	CH ₂ ,CH ₃ bend
1020.38(strong sharp peak)	Flouro Alkanes C-X bend

The FTIR spectral analysis of *R. serpentina* root nanopowders revealed IR bands ranging from 2243.29 cm⁻¹ to 3857.76 cm⁻¹, indicating the presence of C ≡ N stretch, Alkane C-H stretch, intermolecular Alcohol O-H stretch of alcohols, phenols [15], and N-H stretch. *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowders showed peaks ranging from 1020.38 cm⁻¹ to 3439.19 cm⁻¹, confirming the presence of intermolecular alcohol O-H stretch, Alkane C-H stretch, C=C stretch alkene [15], [8], CH₂, CH₃ bend, Flouro Alkanes C-X bend. Several functional groups in *R. serpentina* root nanopowders and *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowders may be linked to their strong biological activities [10], [8], [24],[22]. The occurrence of O-H stretching and C-H groups in the current study might be attributed to the presence of polyphenols, flavanoids and terpenes, respectively [20]. Polyphenols are indicated by an FTIR signal at 900, 1500, 1714, 3000 and 3100 cm⁻¹ [11],[9]. The occurrence of N-H stretching might be attributed to the presence of alkaloids. The FTIR spectrum analysis of *R. serpentina* root methanolic nanopowder resembles the FTIR peaks obtained from AgNps of *R. serpentina* root [5].

In vitro Anticancer activity

Methanolic nanopowder extracts of *Rauwolfia serpentina* root and *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* leaf were tested for cytotoxic activity using the MTT assay against three distinct cell lines: A549 (Human Lung Cancer Cell line), HCT 116 (Human Colon Cancer Cell line) and HL 60 (Human Acute Leukemia Cell line). The MTT colorimetric assay converts yellow tetrazolium salt (MTT) into insoluble formazan crystals using mitochondrial enzymes of live cells. The crystals purple colour is in direct proportion to the number of viable cells, which can be determined by a spectrophotometer at 570nm. Different concentrations of nanopowder extracts—25 µg/ml, 50 µg/ml, 200 µg/ml, and 400 µg/ml—are used to measure cytotoxic activity. Positive control is medium with cells and 15 µM of Camptothecin; negative control is medium without experimental drug.

Table III shows the percentage of cell viability for each of the three cell lines at various concentrations of *R. serpentina* root and *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowders.

The IC₅₀ is the dose of methanolic nanopowder at which 50% of cell viability is achieved. Table IV and Figure 5 provide the IC₅₀ concentrations of *R. serpentina* root and *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowders for each of the three cell lines.

Table III. Cell viability % at different concentrations ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) on various cell lines

Plant part	25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	400 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	standard control	Blank
HL60							
<i>R. serpentina</i> root	92.79	80.78	65.32	49.34	30.23	44.80	100
<i>R. tetraphylla</i> leaf	96.24	80.62	62.66	45.11	21.82	44.80	100
HCT116							
<i>R. serpentina</i> root	98.57	86.79	73.09	55.08	43.32	52.20	100
<i>R. tetraphylla</i> leaf	99.43	90.86	80.47	65.72	53.17	52.20	100
A549							
<i>R. serpentina</i> root	94.68	81.93	70.74	51.29	35.53	43.62	100
<i>R. tetraphylla</i> leaf	84.20	73.28	51.74	43.77	31.49	43.62	100

Table IV. MTT test results

S. NO	Sample name	Test parameter-MTT		
		IC ₅₀		
		A549	HCT116	HL 60
1	<i>R. serpentina</i> root	222.85	283.94	187
2	<i>R. tetraphylla</i> leaf	144.63	532.77	155.28

Figure 5. Comparative overlay of IC₅₀ concentration

Cytotoxic investigation against the HL 60 cell lines

Nanopowders of *R. tetraphylla* leaf produced 21.82% cell viability at 400 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration (Figure 6B), whereas *R. serpentina* root produced 30.23% cell viability at the same dose (Figure 6A). Compared to the standard drug used for the study, the IC₅₀ concentrations of *R. serpentina* root nanopowder and *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowder are 187 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 155.28 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (Figure 5), respectively, indicating good cytotoxic potential. Plates 1A and 1B display the results that were obtained.

Figure 6(A) Cytotoxicity of *R. serpentina* root nanopowders on HL60 (B) Cytotoxicity of *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowders on HL60

Plate 1. Cytotoxicity of *R. serpentina* root nanopowders on HL60 cell line (B) Cytotoxicity of *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowders on HL60 cell line

R. serpentina root and *R. tetraphylla* leaf methanolic nanopowders demonstrated an effective response on various cancer cell lines. Both of these plant's herbal nanopowders shown good effects on the HL60 leukemia cell line, with IC₅₀ doses of 187 µg/ml and 155.28 µg/ml, respectively, in comparison to the study's reference medication, camptothecin (15 µM). *R. serpentina* root nanopowder achieves the maximum suppression of cell viability of 30.23% at 400 µg/ml; cell viability of 21.82% is obtained at same concentration by *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowder. There were no earlier reports of the cytotoxic effects of *R. serpentina* and *R. tetraphylla* on HL 60 cell lines.

Cytotoxic investigation against the HCT 116 cell line

At 400 µg/ml concentration, *R. serpentina* root nanopowders created 43.32% (Figure 7A) and *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowders produced 53.17% (Figure 7B) cell viability, indicating both nanopowders strong cytotoxic potential. The IC₅₀ concentrations for *R. serpentina* root nanopowders and *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowders are 283.94 µg/ml and 532.77 µg/ml (Figure 5), respectively. Plates 2A and 2B displayed the effected cell lines.

Figure 7. Cytotoxicity of *R. serpentina* root nanopowders on HCT116 (A) Cytotoxicity of *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowders on HCT116 (B)

Plate 2 (A) Cytotoxicity of *R. serpentina* root nanopowders on HCT 116 cell line (B) Cytotoxicity of *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowders on HCT- 116 cell lines

R. serpentina root nanopowder and *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowder were shown to efficiently suppress HCT116 cell viability. They exhibited an antiproliferative impact of 43.32% and 53.17%, respectively, with IC₅₀ concentrations of 283.94 µg/ml and 532.77 µg/ml. Hemidesmus indicus methanolic extract is consistent with these results [23].

Cytotoxic investigation against the A549 cell lines

At a concentration of 400 µg/ml, *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowders produced 31.49% cell viability (Figure 8B), whereas *R. serpentina* root nanopowders produced 35.53% cell viability (Figure 8A). The test compounds demonstrated high cytotoxic potential, with IC₅₀ concentrations of 144.63 µg/ml and 222.85 µg/ml, respectively (Figure 5), as compared to the reference drug utilized in the study. Plates 3A and 3B demonstrate the influence of plant samples on cancer cell lines.

Figure 8. Cytotoxicity of *R. serpentina* root nanopowders on A549 (B) Cytotoxicity of *R. tetraphylla* root nanopowders on A549

Plate 3(A)Cytotoxicity of *R. serpentina* root nanopowders on A549 cell line (B) Cytotoxicity of *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowders on A549 cell lines

According to the results, *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowders exhibit significant cytotoxicity against the cell lines HL 60 and A549, with IC₅₀ concentrations of 155.28 µg/ml and 144.63 µg/ml, respectively. When applied to HL 60 cell lines, *R. serpentina* root nanopowders exhibit significant cytotoxicity, with an IC₅₀ concentration of 187µg/ml.

Cytotoxic study using A549 cell lines showed good cytotoxic potential properties, with *R. serpentina* root nanopowder achieving maximum cell viability of 35.53% with IC₅₀ concentration of 222.85 µg/ml and *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowder achieving maximum cell viability of 31.49% with an IC₅₀ concentration of 144.63 µg/ml. For the first time, *R. serpentina* herbal nano powders were shown to have an anti-proliferative impact on A549 cell lines. There have been reports of Labdane diterpene derived from *R. tetraphylla* having cytotoxic effects on A549 cell lines [6]. Previous studies on *Borreria hispida* seed nanopowders [26], on *Tecoma stans* leaf nanopowders [25] and on *Justica adathoda* gold nanopaticles [18] have shown similar findings.

In the current work, *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowder was shown to have excellent cytotoxic capability against HL60 and A549 cell lines. Methanolic nanopowders of *R. serpentina* root were shown to be potentially cytotoxic to HCT 116 cell lines when compared to *R. tetraphylla* leaf nanopowder. These plants include a wide spectrum of alkaloids and phytochemicals that may be responsible for their anticancer effect [12],[13].

IV. Conclusion

Herbal-based nanopowders have sparked a lot of attention in the growing field of nanotechnology. In our current study, we used a mechanical approach of high energy ball milling to synthesize nanopowders from shade dried parts of our experimental plants for the first time, without the use of harmful chemicals. These Herbal nanopowders generated using ball milling from *Rauwolfia serpentina* and *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* were analyzed using XRD, SEM, UV-VIS Spectroscopy and FTIR. The Cytotoxic study using MTT assay revealed that

methanolic root and leaf nanopowder extracts of *Rauwolfia serpentina* and *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* were cytotoxic against HL 60, HCT 116, and A 549 cell lines, with HL 60 having the most impact. *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* leaf nanopowders shown potential cytotoxicity against HL 60 and A549 cell lines, but *Rauwolfia serpentina* root nanopowder had a substantial impact on HL 60 cell lines.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest for this study.

References

- [1] M. C. Alley, D. A. Scudiero, A. Monks, M. L. Hursey, M. J. Czerwinski, D. L. Fine, B. J. Abbott, J. G. Mayo, R. H. Shoemaker, and M. R. Boyd, "Feasibility of drug screening with panels of human tumor cell lines using a microculture tetrazolium assay," *Cancer Res.*, vol. 48, no. 3, pp. 589–601, 1988.
- [2] S. H. Ansari, F. Islam, and M. Sameem, "Influence of nanotechnology on herbal drugs: a review," *J. Adv. Pharm. Technol. Res.*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 142–146, 2012. doi:10.4103/2231-4040.101006
- [3] S. Bayda, M. Adeel, T. Tuccinardi, M. Cordani, and F. Rizzolio, "The history of nanoscience and nanotechnology: from chemical-physical applications to nanomedicine," *Molecules*, vol. 25, no. 1, p. 112, 2020. doi:10.3390/molecules25010112
- [4] B. Bodaiah, A. M. Anupama, S. Y. Yamini, M. Usha Kiranmayi, B. Pavani Bai, and P. Sudhakar, "Ecofriendly synthesis, physicochemical characterization and catalytic activity of gold nanopowders using plants," *Int. J. Adv. Sci. Res. Manag.*, vol. 3, no. 8, pp. 124–132, 2018.
- [5] B. Bonigala, A. Gudise, Y. S. Yeragorla, A. A. Manne, and S. Poda, "Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles using *Rauwolfia serpentina* roots and screening for their antimicrobial activity," *Int. J. Sci. Res. Rev.*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1400–1411, 2018.
- [6] G. Brahmachari, L. C. Mandal, D. Gorai, A. Mondal, S. Sarkar, and S. Majhi, "A new labdane diterpene from *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* Linn. (Apocynaceae)," *J. Chem. Res.*, vol. 35, no. 12, pp. 678–680, 2011. doi:10.3184/174751911X13220462651507
- [7] R. P. Chauhan, C. Gupta, and D. Prakash, "Methodological advancements in green nanotechnology and their applications in biological synthesis of herbal nanopowders," *Int. J. Bioassays*, vol. 1, no. 7, pp. 6–10, 2012.
- [8] J. Coates, "Interpretation of infrared spectra, a practical approach," in *Encyclopedia of Analytical Chemistry*, R. A. Meyers, Ed. Hoboken, NJ, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2000. doi:10.1002/9780470027318.a5606
- [9] S. M. Dhivya and K. Kalaichelvi, "UV-Vis spectroscopic and FTIR analysis of *Sarcostemma brevistigma* Wight & Arn.," *Int. J. Herbal Med.*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 1–4, 2017. doi:10.22159/ijcpr.2017.v9i3.18890
- [10] P. A. Gerakines, W. A. Schutte, J. M. Greenberg, and E. F. van Dishoeck, "The infrared band strengths of H₂O, CO and CO₂ in laboratory simulations of astrophysical ice mixtures," *Astron. Astrophys.*, vol. 296, no. 3, pp. 810–818, 1995.
- [11] M. G. Geethu, P. S. Suchitra, C. H. Kavitha, J. M. Aswathy, D. Babu, and K. Murugan, "Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy analysis of different solvent extracts of water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes* Mart. Solms.): an allelopathic approach," *World J. Pharm. Pharm. Sci.*, vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 1256–1266, 2014.
- [12] A. A. M. Iqbal, F. A. K. Khan, and M. Khan, "Ethno-phyto-pharmacological overview on *Rauwolfia tetraphylla* L.," *Int. J. Pharm. Phytopharmacol. Res.*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 247–251, 2013.
- [13] M. D. Jakaria, S. M. Tareq, M. Ibrahim, and S. Bokhtearuddin, "*Rauwolfia tetraphylla* L. (Apocynaceae): a pharmacognostical, phytochemical and pharmacological review," *J. Chem. Pharm. Res.*, vol. 8, no. 12, pp. 114–120, 2016.

- [14] H. A. Jeng and J. Swanson, "Toxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles in mammalian cells," *J. Environ. Sci. Health A*, vol. 41, no. 12, pp. 2699–2711, 2006. doi:10.1080/10934520600966177
- [15] K. Jyoti, M. Baunthiyal, and A. Singh, "Characterization of silver nanoparticles synthesized using *Urtica dioica* Linn. leaves and their synergistic effects with antibiotics," *J. Radiat. Res. Appl. Sci.*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 217–227, 2016. doi:10.1016/j.jrras.2015.10.002
- [16] S. Karthik, R. Suriyaprabha, K. S. Balu, P. Manivasakan, and V. Rajendran, "Influence of ball milling on the particle size and antimicrobial properties of *Tridax procumbens* leaf nanoparticles," *IET Nanobiotechnol.*, vol. 11, pp. 12–17, 2017. doi:10.1049/iet-nbt.2016.0028
- [17] M. Kaur, G. Singh, K. Khanna, and N. Kaur, "Nanotechnology: a review," in *Proc. Second Nat. Conf. Adv. Manuf. Syst.*, Ferozpur, India: SBS State Technical Campus, 2015.
- [18] D. Latha, P. Prabu, C. Arulvasu, R. Manikandan, S. Sampurnam, and V. Narayanan, "Enhanced cytotoxic effect on human lung carcinoma cell line (A549) by gold nanoparticles synthesized from *Justicia adhatoda* leaf extract," *Asian Pac. J. Trop. Biomed.*, vol. 8, no. 11, pp. 540–547, 2018. doi:10.4103/2221-1691.245969
- [19] K. Lingaraju, H. R. Naika, K. Manjunath, G. Nagaraju, D. Suresh, and H. Nagabhushana, "Rauvolfia serpentina-mediated green synthesis of CuO nanoparticles and its multidisciplinary studies," *Acta Metall. Sin. Engl. Lett.*, vol. 28, no. 9, pp. 1134–1140, 2015.
- [20] M. A. G. Maobe and R. M. Nyarango, "Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer analysis of *Urtica dioica* medicinal herb used for the treatment of diabetes, malaria and pneumonia in Kisii region, southwest Kenya," *World Appl. Sci. J.*, vol. 21, no. 8, pp. 1128–1135, 2013. doi:10.5829/idosi.wasj.2013.21.8.2876
- [21] T. Mosmann, "Rapid colorimetric assay for cellular growth and survival: application to proliferation and cytotoxicity assays," *J. Immunol. Methods*, vol. 65, no. 1–2, pp. 55–63, 1983. doi:10.1016/0022-1759(83)90303-4
- [22] A. B. D. Nandiyanto, R. Oktiani, and R. Ragadhita, "How to read and interpret FTIR spectroscopy of organic material," *Indones. J. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 4, no. 1, p. 97, 2019. doi:10.17509/ijost.v4i1.15806
- [23] Nutan, N. Kumar, and G. Saxena, "Cytotoxic effect of *Hemidesmus indicus* R. Br. on HCT-116 human colon cell lines," *Pharma Innov. J.*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 86–89, 2019.
- [24] S. C. Okereke, I. I. Ijeh, and U. O. Arunsi, "Determination of bioactive constituents of *Rauvolfia vomitoria* Afzel roots using GC-MS and FT-IR," *Afr. J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 25–31, 2017. doi:10.5897/AJPP2016.4712
- [25] J. P. Robinson, S. Kumaresan, S. Ramasamy, and P. Ponnusamy, "Antioxidant and cytotoxic activity of *Tecoma stans* against lung cancer cell line (A549)," *Braz. J. Pharm. Sci.*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 1–5, 2017. doi:10.1590/s2175-97902017000300204
- [26] S. Rupachandra and D. V. Sarada, "Induction of apoptotic effects of antiproliferative protein from the seeds of *Borreria hispida* on lung cancer (A549) and cervical cancer (HeLa) cell lines," *Biomed Res. Int.*, vol. 2014, p. 179836, 2014. doi:10.1155/2014/179836
- [27] R. K. Sanjukta, D. Samir, K. Puro, S. Ghataak, L. Shakuntal, and A. Sen, "Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles using plants," *Int. J. Nanomed. Nanosurg.*, vol. 2, no. 2, 2016. doi:10.16966/2470-3206.110
- [28] R. Singh and V. D. Mendhulkar, "FTIR studies and spectrophotometric analysis of natural antioxidants, polyphenols and flavonoids in *Abutilon indicum* (Linn.) Sweet leaf extract," *J. Chem. Pharm. Res.*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 205–211, 2015.
- [29] S. Singh and S. Sedha, "Medicinal plants and their pharmacological aspects," *Food Pharma Int.*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 156–170, 2018. doi:10.5530/fpi.1.4.1
- [30] K. Vijaya Kumar, G. Rosaiah, K. Babu, N. Tirupati Swamy, and N. Krishna, "A study on antimicrobial properties of herbal nanopowders of selected mangrove plants," *Res. J. Life Sci. Bioinform. Pharm. Chem. Sci.*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 498–512, 2018.
- [31] R. J. Vakil, "Rauvolfia serpentina in the treatment of high blood pressure: a review of the literature," *Circulation*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 220–229, 1955. doi:10.1161/01.cir.12.2.220
- [32] S. P. Vinay, Udayabhanu, G. Nagaraju, C. Chandrappa, and N. Chandrasekhar, "Rauvolfia tetraphylla-mediated green synthesis of Ag nanoparticles: applications to anticancer, antioxidant and antimutagenic," *J. Clust. Sci.*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 1–20, 2019. doi:10.1007/s10876-019-01598-5
- [33] L. Zhang, T. Tsuzuki, and X. Wang, "Preparation of cellulose nanofiber from softwood pulp by ball milling," *Cellulose*, vol. 22, pp. 1729–1741, 2015. doi:10.1007/s10570-015-0582-6

